

PROFESSIONAL CULTURE AND MORAL VALUES OF MODERN LEADERS

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Annotation. In this article, by developing the professional activities of modern leaders, deepening the reforms to build a legal state and civil society in New Uzbekistan is carried out on the basis of the main strategic goal of the state. Also, in order to restore and develop the traditions of national statehood in the spheres of state and society construction, the author's scientific analyzes and opinions have formed important foundations for the formation of the professional culture of modern leaders based on spiritual factors.

Keywords. New Uzbekistan, modern leaders, state, society, professional culture of leaders, culture, spirituality, culture, values.

Introduction

Spirituality is an important factor in the political activities of leading personnel as an aspect of human essence, a special form of existence and expression of existence. "Spirituality is not a gift of fate. In order for spirituality to be perfected in a person's heart, he must work with his heart and conscience, mind and hand. This treasure gives a person stability in life, his views do not allow him to make a living on the path of gaining wealth." The legal basis for the establishment of a democratic state, the protection of human rights and freedoms, which is considered an important condition for the establishment of a new Uzbekistan, is being created, and large-scale reforms are being implemented. Adoption of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 21, 2022 on measures for the implementation of administrative reforms in Uzbekistan № . PF-269¹ is of great importance in the formation of the professional culture of leading personnel based on spiritual factors in order to restore and develop the traditions of national statehood in the fields of state and community building. In accordance with the

¹ Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг Фармони, 21.12.2022 йилдаги ПФ-269-сон. (lex.uz).

requirements of this Decree², to form a compact public administration system that meets modern requirements in the conditions of New Uzbekistan, to increase the responsibility of the heads of state bodies by simplifying the processes of decision-making and consideration of the issue, and to direct their activities to effectiveness, as well as to restore the traditions of national statehood in the fields of state and community building. and for the purpose of development, important attention is paid to the formation of the professional culture of the leading personnel on the basis of spiritual factors³.

Literature analysis.

If we look at the past of the Uzbek people, we can see that there have been a lot of statesmen in our history, and their activities were also unique. It contained scientific-theoretical concepts and views related to the political elite and political leadership, Western and Eastern schools. These teachings serve as an important theoretical and practical⁴ basis for studying the problems related to the formation and development of leaders and management personnel in the state management system of Uzbekistan. In particular, the great scholars who lived and worked in Central Asia, Al-Khorazmi, Abu Nasr Farabi, Abu Rayhan Beruni, Amir Temur, Sharafuddin Ali Yazdi, Nizamulmulk, Khondamir, Yusuf Khos Hajib, Mahmud Kashgari, Alisher Navoi, Narshahi, Samandar Termizi⁵, are in the history of our national statehood. the issue of personnel is analyzed politically and philosophically through the concepts of "mayor", "city mayor", "leader", "leadership". In addition, state and public figures learned from great statesmen such as Sharaf Rashidov, Islam Karimov, who performed good deeds for the well-being of the people, carried out creative works and earned the respect and honor of the people, and the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Miromonovich Mirziyoyev, who is currently in leadership. worth it. Our great ancestors made a worthy contribution to the development of not only the Uzbek people, but also the peace and tranquility of the nations of the world, and the development of scientific civilization with their fair politics, high spirituality, and intellectual potential. In today's fast-paced era, changes in people's consciousness require everyone to take a deep look at the changes taking place in the world. In particular, this process places great responsibility on leaders. Since the first period of independence in the country, as the issues of inculcating national and spiritual values into the activities of the leading personnel rose to the level of state policy, this process became one of the components of the reforms. Shavkat Miromonovich Mirziyoyev was elected President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on December 4, 2016, and his reforms were carried out based on the principle that "government agencies should serve the people, not the people."⁶ - Leaders should serve not only the state, but also people and families, to ensure their legitimate interests. In the formation of the professional culture of the leading personnel, feeding from national spiritual sources, conducting scientific research in such fields as ensuring that the processes of modernization of the country are carried out on the basis of justice and spirituality criteria have become not only one of the urgent tasks of the current era, but also a guarantee of the development of the country's political system based on democratic principles. is happening Because one of the main tasks of the state is to ensure that the principles of justice are followed in management. If we pay attention to the fact that spiritual factors act as the main criteria in this process, it becomes self-evident how important the topic is. By the time of national independence, a wide path was opened for the development of our national spirituality⁷.

Summary

The rise of our spiritual life, which our independence paved the way for: restoration of our national consciousness, national pride and pride, allows us to educate our young generation in this way, changes the spiritual and ideological world of our society today, and draws the attention of others to the

² Мирзиёев.Ш «Халқ давлат идораларига эмас, балки давлат органлари халқимизга хизмат қилиши керак» 31.08.2017. <https://kun.uz/news>.

³ Каримов.И. Жамиятимизни эркинлаштириш, ислохотларни чуқурлаштириш, маънавиятимизни юксалтириш ва халқимизнинг ҳаёт даражасини ошириш — барча ишларимизнинг мезони ва мақсадидир. 15-жилд. –Т.: Ўзбекистон, 2007. –Б.3-4.

⁴ Форобий Абу Наср. Фозил одамлар шахри. -Т.: Халқ мероси, 1998. -186 б.

⁵ Амир Темур ва Темурийлар мавзуга бағишлаб яратилган йирик асарлар.

⁶ Masharipov, I. B. (2018). Transforming Civil Society in Transition Period and Its Certain Issues. Eastern European Scientific Journal,

⁷ Машарипов, И. Б. (2009). Маънавий омилларнинг раҳбар кадрлар касбий маданиятини шакллантиришдаги ўрни. Сиёсий фанлар номзоди илмий даражасини олиш учун ёзилган диссертация. Тошкент-2009,-Б, 17.

appearance, worldview and qualities of the original Uzbek nation⁸, our strength, our energy adding enthusiasm. In general, the relevance of the issue of paying significant attention to moral factors in the formation of the professional culture of leading personnel by the state is determined by the following:

Firstly, in the conditions of democratic development based on the spirit of national independence, it has become a vital necessity to pay attention to spiritual factors in order to ensure civil unity and cohesion in the society. The main reason for this is liberating our society, deepening reforms, improving our spirituality and raising the standard of living of our people - the criterion and goal of all our work. Democratic freedoms and opportunities of civil society can be widely and effectively used only by highly moral people;

Secondly, in the conditions of improvement and liberalization of the society and state management, it is possible to mobilize their activities towards development and creativity only as a result of inculcating high spiritual qualities into their worldviews. After all, the development and prospects of the society and the state are determined in many aspects by the high moral image of the leading personnel, which has been proven in history;

Thirdly, in the conditions of building a legal state and a civil society in New Uzbekistan, researching the theoretical and methodological aspects of the importance of spiritual factors in the formation of the professional culture of leading personnel, studying the issue of the dialectical interrelationship between spiritual values and the professional culture of leading personnel has become an important urgent task;

Fourthly, tasks such as revealing the role of moral factors in the formation of the professional culture of modern management personnel, substantiating these processes, finding problems and their solutions in this field, and formulating proposals and recommendations on the effective use of moral factors in the formation of the professional culture of management personnel during the research of the topic are structural aspects of the state's personnel policy. came from the need to emphasize that it is one of the parts;

Fifth, to inculcate moral and ethical qualities in the formation of the professional culture of managerial personnel in Uzbekistan, to study the factors that positively affect the moral and ethical development of managerial personnel, to generalize, improve and enrich the national experience in this field, as well as to interpret them in relation to the requirements of the current era. that the formation of new proposals and recommendations in order to eliminate problems in this field has become one of the bases of training and selection of modern management personnel;

Sixth, in the present period, the actual tasks of studying the specific characteristics of the level of development of the spiritual aspects of the professional culture of the leading personnel, forming the main criteria in this field, generalizing the methods of wide use of spiritual factors in the process of personnel training, and presenting them to training centers for training and gaining experience that it is gaining importance as Development of the role of spiritual factors in the formation of the professional culture of modern leaders in new Uzbekistan has always attracted the attention of political leaders, scientists and thinkers⁹. Especially from the first days of independence, it is necessary to train modern leaders, to ensure their professional maturity, in this process to pay attention to the spiritual and moral qualities of the personnel, to form a sense of responsibility for the destiny of the Motherland and the people in the activities of the leaders¹⁰. The theoretical views on the role of spiritual factors in the management of the state and society in the professional culture of state officials are expressed in the works of Abu Nasr Farabi, a great thinker. Also, in the Tuzuks of Sohigiron Amir Temur, the theoretical views on the training of state officials and the formation of their professional culture and their practical importance are deeply revealed. scientific-theoretical analysis of the need to develop moral factors in the

⁸ Masharipov, M. B. (2021). Non-governmental non-profit organizations are the main institution of civil society. In *Наука сегодня: проблемы и пути решения* (pp. 100-101).

⁹Batirovich, M. I. (2024). FACTORS OF DEVELOPMENT PROCESSES OF SOCIO-POLITICAL BASES OF NGOS IN NEW UZBEKISTAN. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH* ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 13(01), 16-21.

¹⁰Masharipov, I. B. (2023). Relevance of civil society in the modern world, attitude and solutions. *International Journal of Inclusive and Sustainable Education*, 2(7), 53.

formation of the professional culture of leading personnel;

- the role of leading personnel in state and community management, the importance of inculcating spiritual values into their worldview in the social and political development of the state, identifying the problems that have arisen in this area and finding their solutions;

- to determine the level of formation of the spiritual aspects of the professional culture of the leading personnel, as well as to develop a system of criteria reflecting its essence in this process;

- practical experiences from a political point of view of political-spiritual processes related to the activities of leading personnel in society

Attention was also paid to the views of famous thinkers and scientists who lived in our country on leadership spirituality and management culture, opinions and conclusions of world-renowned political scientists, politicians and philosophers.

- justifying that increasing the importance of moral factors, which are an important aspect of forming the professional culture of leading personnel, ensures the implementation of public administration in the country based on national interests;

- to reveal that it makes it possible for the leading personnel to strive for spiritual "acme" and that the professional activity of the leading personnel is a guarantee of achieving important social goals;

- to prove that "acme" is the highest, ideal level of the leader in the process of spiritual improvement, characterized by the optimal level of the leader's spiritual development and the harmony of his ability to use his life experience;

- justifying the importance of improving the moral qualities of the management personnel in the current period, along with the professional skills;

- to improve the process of spiritual development of leading personnel, to substantiate the consideration of subjective and objective factors affecting these processes, to prove the demands and needs for the spiritual growth of leading personnel, and also to reveal that the main direction of the professional activity of a leader is to harmonize the direction of his activity with the interests of society and the state. to give

- creation of conditions for the moral improvement of management personnel at the level of the management personnel training system, including strengthening of moral and educational education and training in management personnel training and retraining centers, further strengthening of the legal basis of ethical and moral requirements for management personnel, retraining of personnel for the purpose of organizing modern social and political centers, summarizing theoretical views and practical experiences on increasing the role of national and spiritual values in improving their professional culture and presenting them to practice in this field.

- in order for the leader's professional activity to be focused on achieving socially important goals, it has been repeatedly researched from the point of view of political science that humanism, justice, respect and attention to the human being, honoring the honor and dignity of each person are the main principles of the leader's activity;

- the criteria for determining the level of mastery of spiritual values in the formation of the professional culture of the leading personnel were brought into one system based on the summarization of the results of historical experience and modern practice;

- connecting the professional activities of the leading personnel with spiritual values, in this process, the requirements of national interests are set as the main direction of the activities of the leading personnel, it was revealed how important the role of spiritual factors is in ensuring that their activities in the way of the freedom and prosperity of the Motherland take place in a general and common way;

- objective and subjective factors affecting the process of wide use of moral factors in the formation of the professional culture of the leading personnel were identified, methodological and practical recommendations and proposals were developed for their use;

- theoretical analyzes were formed to increase the effectiveness of the management personnel's activities, to ensure that their work activities are based on the expression of the interests of the population, through the means of expanding the assimilation of moral values in the system of training and retraining

of management personnel;

- the importance of ideological-ideological factors in the formation of the professional culture of the leading personnel was substantiated; - the role of the idea of national independence as a unifying force capable of uniting citizens in society, increasing their labor and social activity was revealed; It can be seen that researching the importance of the role of spiritual factors in the formation of the professional culture of the leading personnel in the formation of the reforms of the formation of New Uzbekistan, the restoration of national and spiritual values in the country, and the formation of the theoretical aspects of the reforms in this field have been scientifically analyzed. is one of the most urgent tasks.

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